

Fenton syndrome about a case and review of the literature

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Summary: - Fenton's naviculo-capital syndrome or scapho-capital fracture is a very rare lesion, often overlooked. It results from high-energy wrist trauma. Its mechanism is controversial. It is most often associated with carpal dislocation. Forced extension appears to be the most frequent etiology; fracture of the scaphoid by compression makes hyperextension of the wrist possible, thus allowing contact between the posterior horn of the lunate and the proximal pole of the capitate which is fractured and tilted from 180°. The dorsal approach allowed a reduction of the capitate as well as contention by pinning the first row, independently of the second row. The scapholunate and lunaro-triquetral interosseous ligaments were intact. The anterior approach allows a good reduction of the scaphoid while preserving its vascularization. An antebrachio-palmar cast immobilization was put in place for 12 weeks. The rehabilitation lasted six months. Two years later, the Cooney functional score was good and all the fractures had healed without any intracarpal misalignment. Return to work was in the eighth months after the accident.

Conclusion: Hypertensive disorders of pregnancy (HDP) are influenced by various factors, with older maternal age and obesity being the most common. The incidence of hypertensive disorders of pregnancy varies based on race, socioeconomic status, age, and parity. Creating awareness of the risks associated with hypertensive disorders of pregnancy is essential. Pregnant women with hypertensive disorders require frequent antenatal visits to ensure appropriate outcomes.

Keywords: Scaphoid; Fracture; Wrist dislocations; Fracture of the capitate; Fenton syndrome.

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Introduction:

Fenton syndrome is a rare anatomic entity, associating a fracture of the scaphoid with that of the capitate [1]. Its mechanism remains a subject of controversy today. It is defined by a transverse fracture of the proximal pole of the capitate, with a rotation of 90 to 180° of the latter and a fracture of the scaphoid. Rotation of the proximal pole of the large bone is sometimes absent. Its clinical diagnosis is difficult because the examination does not differ from other traumatic lesions of the carpus, however standard radiology of the face, profile and oblique views most often allows the diagnosis to be made. Treatment must be early and surgical, because on the one hand the rotation of the proximal pole of the large bone by 180° cannot be reduced by external maneuvers [2], on the other hand it prevents complications such as necrosis and pseudarthrosis. The aim of this work is to discuss the injury mechanisms, diagnostic problems, and our therapeutic conduct in the light of a review of the literature.

Observation:

This is a 29-year-old patient, right-handed, day laborer, who presented following a fall from a high place, with landing on the palm of the left hand, wrist in extension, trauma to the wrist. left, with pain and total functional impotence. After a careful clinical

examination which did not reveal a paralysis of the median nerve, the radiographic assessment and a CT scan of the wrist showed a posterior trans-scaphoperilunate dislocation associated with a fracture of the proximal pole of the capitate and 180° tilt of the latter (Vance type III)[3](Fig. 1).The patient underwent emergency surgery, under general anesthesia, and a tourniquet at the root of the limb. The approach is dorsal.Longitudinal, centered on the radiocarpal space (Fig.2), between the third and fourth extensor compartments,The posterior interosseous nerve was coagulated. The anatomical reduction was then carried out manually under visual control, using a pin and spatula. The pinning of the first row of the carpal bones is prepared by placing two crossed Kirschner wires introduced from the lunate facet of the scaphoid and two others at the level of the triquetrum. The osteosynthesis of the capitate was carried out by crossed pinning of the second row, the two pins end at the proximal pole of the capitate (Fig. 3), concerning the scaphoidium the plugging was carried out by an anterior route.

An antebrachio-palmar cast immobilization, taking the first phalanx of the thumb and maintaining the wrist in a neutral position, is put in place for 12 weeks. The pins are removed under local anesthesia. The rehabilitation lasted six months.

At 1 year follow-up, the functional result was very satisfactory. Clinically, the Cooney functional score was good: extension was 50°; bending at 40°; the average clamping force was 78% compared to the healthy side. Radiologically, all the fractures have consolidated and there is no intra-carpal misalignment in DISI or VISI (Figure 3). No complications were noted either following the operation or in the long term. Return to work was in the eighth months after the accident.

Discussion:

The scaphocapital fracture is a rare injury, the mechanism of which is controversial. Indeed, for Fenton [1], the double fracture is due to a fall on the hand, with the wrist extended and in radial inclination. The radial styloid fractures the scaphoid, then the residual energy fractures the proximal pole of the large bone, which undergoes a lateral thrust responsible for tilting in the frontal plane. Adler [2], Marsh [4], Van Cauwenberghe [5], proposed related mechanisms. This mechanism is insufficient to explain the frequent association with perilunate dislocation of the carpus. Stein [6], proposed a more satisfactory mechanism; the fall occurs on the palm of the hand, the wrist in forced extension leads to a fracture of the scaphoid only by compression, without radial styloid-scaphoid contact. This fracture allows the hyperextension necessary for the contact between the posterior margin of the radius and the neck of the capitate, responsible for the fracture of the capitate. Continuing the movement results in a 90° rotation of the proximal pole of the fractured capitate; a further 90° rotation occurs when returning to neutral position. These two rotations in the same direction result in a 180° circular movement of the proximal pole of the capitate in the sagittal plane. Johnson [7] specifies that during hyperextension of the wrist, if the head of the capitate does not dislocate posteriorly, the lunate can decapitate the large bone with its posterior margin. Vance [3] does not eliminate a bending mechanism in certain cases. In this case the anterior margin of the radius would come into contact with the neck of the capitate, after the fracture of the scaphoid.

For our part, we believe that hyperextension of the wrist in ulnar tilt will lead to a fracture of the scaphoid and rupture of the anterior carpal ligaments which maintain the concavity and stability of the latter. The radius and the proximal pole of the scaphoid as well as the lunate form a single block, which following the exaggeration of hyperextension, will decapitate the capitate by a “corkscrew” effect and will also lead to a fracture of the triquetrum by avulsion of the lunotriquetral ligament. Clinical diagnosis is difficult, reflected by the delay in diagnosis which is a very common phenomenon [8] and especially since there is no associated dislocation. The fracture of the scaphoid is usually diagnosed, but the lesion of the capitate goes unnoticed, the diagnosis is then made remotely during checks. It is therefore necessary for any fracture of the scaphoid to pay particular attention to the radiological images of the capitate and triquetrum. The clinic will also look for an associated nerve injury (median nerve damage)

Standard front and profile radiography confirms the diagnosis. The lateral image makes it possible to classify the lesions according to the Vance criteria [3]: type 1: the carpus is aligned, without any dislocated element; Type 2: dorsal dislocation of the carpus, taking away the proximal pole of the capitate; Type 3: dorsal dislocation of the carpus, the proximal pole of the capitate remaining in the

concavity of the lunate; Type 4: only the proximal pole of the capitate is dorsally dislocated; Type 5: palmar dislocation of the carpus with the proximal pole of the capitate; Type 6: isolated palmar dislocation of the proximal pole of the capitate. Our patient had a type 3 lesion with the proximal pole of the capitate remaining in the concavity of the lunate.

This lesion is common while the first three types represent the majority of scapho-capital fractures. Vance finds only one case of types 4, 5, and 6 in the literature.

Sometimes the CT scan is necessary to complete the assessment. Dislocation of the carpal bones is often associated with scaphocapital fracture. This is of course an element aggravating the picture and a factor of compression of the median nerve [8]. If surgical treatment does not seem to be discussed, the approach must be chosen according to the anatomical lesions and respect for the Vascular anatomy. The anterior approach is logical in cases of damage to the median nerve (nerve decompression by opening of the carpal tunnel) or in cases of ligamentous lesions (ligamentous repair). This anterior approach preserves the vascularization of the carpal bones, avoiding pseudo osteoarthritis and necrosis of the latter, however the reduction of fractures is very laborious due to the limited daylight. In other cases, the posterior approach is the most used, it must remain median to avoid any risk of necrosis of the scaphoid. The vascularization of the capitate is distal according to Razemont [9], which explains the low risk of damage during a dislocation, or during an approach if it remains proximal. On the other hand, the scaphoid is vascularized dorsally, with penetration holes over the entire distal third according to Watson [10], leading to a greater risk during the posterior approach and reduction and osteosynthesis maneuvers. The posterior approach makes it possible to reduce the dislocation of the carpus and the tilting of the proximal pole of the capitate, something which is impossible by external maneuvers [11]. It controls all carpal bone lesions in the majority of cases [12-14]. A complementary palmar approach can be useful in cases of irreducibility via the dorsal route alone, the case of our patient. Rare authors have recommended a solely palmar approach, particularly for trans-scapho-perilunate forms [15]. The current trend is towards the systematic combined palmar and dorsal approach [16-18]. In forms associated with perilunate dislocation, reduction of the dislocation by external maneuvers is not recommended, the surgical approach is systematic. Emergency resection of the first row of the carpus is only possible in the event of excision of the proximal pole of the scaphoid, made necessary by the high risk of necrosis, when the bone fragment is completely free on the posterior surface of the radius. . This resection of the proximal pole of the scaphoid destabilizes the carpus and prompts a resection of the first row of the carpus and maintaining the carpal height using an external distraction fixator. It can be carried out in a single stage with osteosynthesis of the capitate or in two stages. [19,20]. The first step is the synthesis of the capitate due to the excellent vascularization of the distal part of the capitate as recommended by Weseley [20] to obtain a good quality carpal neocondyle (the head of the capitate must be free from any cartilaginous lesion), then a second stage of resection of the first row.

Conclusion:

Fenton naviculocapital syndrome represents a rare lesion, often associated with carpal dislocation. Before any trans-scaphopilunate

dislocation, and any isolated fracture of the scaphoid, it is necessary to look for a fracture of the large bone. The treatment is surgical, requiring the least aggressive approach possible, and the treatment of associated tears.

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Figures:

Figure 1: X-ray of the right wrist from the front and in profile with the scanner: transtuberular fracture of the carpal scaphoid associated with a fracture of the capitate rotated by 180° causing Fenton syndrome

Figure 2: Preoperative view: posterior approach: capitate fracture

Figure 3: Control x-rays after pinning the carpal bones